

Neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti and Modified Neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti Indices of Certain Dendrimers

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 21 March 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: V.R. Kulli</p>	<p>In this paper, we introduce the neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti index, modified neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti index and their corresponding exponentials of a graph. Also we compute these neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti indices of certain dendrimers. Furthermore, we establish some properties of newly defined the neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti index.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti index, modified neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti index, dendrimer.</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

Let G be a finite, simple, connected graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The degree $d_G(u)$ of a vertex u is the number of vertices adjacent to u . Let $S_G(u)$ denote the sum of the degrees of all vertices adjacent to a vertex u . We refer [1] for undefined notations and terminologies.

A graph index is a numerical parameter mathematically derived from the graph structure. Many graph indices have been considered in Theoretical Chemistry and several graph indices were defined by using vertex degree concept [2]. The Zagreb, Gourava, Nirmala, Sombor, Revan, E-Bahhatti indices are the most degree based graph indices in Chemical Graph Theory, see [3-39]. Graph indices have their applications in various disciplines in Science and Technology [40-41].

The Kepler Bahhatti index [42] of a graph G is defined as

$$KB(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [(d_G(u) + d_G(v)) + \sqrt{d_G(u)^2 + d_G(v)^2}].$$

Recently, some Kepler Bahhatti indices were studied in [43-46].

The neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti index of a graph G is defined as

$$NKB(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} ((S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}).$$

Considering the neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti index, we introduce the neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti exponential of a graph G and defined it as

$$NKB(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{(S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}}.$$

We define the modified neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti index of a graph G as

$${}^m NKB(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{(S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}}.$$

Considering the modified neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti index, we introduce the modified neighborhood Kepler Bahhatti exponential of a graph G and defined it as

$${}^m NKB(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{(S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}} x^{(S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}}.$$

Recently, some neighborhood indices were studied in [47-53].

In 2011 [54], Graovac et al. introduced the fifth M -Zagreb indices (now we call the first and second neighborhood indices) defined as

$$NM_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [S_G(u) + S_G(v)],$$

$$NM_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} S_G(u)S_G(v)$$

The neighborhood Sombor index [55] of a molecular graph G is defined as

$$NSO(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}$$

In this paper, we compute the neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi index, modified neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi index and their corresponding exponentials of certain families of dendrimers.

2. RESULTYS FOR PAMAM DENDRIMER $PD_1[n]$

We consider the PAMAM dendrimers with n growth stages, denoted by $PD_1[n]$ for every $n \geq 0$, see Figure 1.

Figure 1. PAMAM dendrimer $PD_1[n]$

Let G be the graph of PAMAM dendrimer $PD_1[n]$. By calculation, we see that G has $12 \times 2^{n+2} - 23$ vertices and $12 \times 2^{n+2} - 24$ edges. Also the edge partition of the form (2,3), (3,4), (3,5), (4,5), (5,5), (5,6) for PAMAM dendrimer $PD_1[n]$ based on the degree sum of neighbors of end vertices of each edge is obtained, as given in Table 1.

Table 1

$S_G(u), S_G(v) \setminus uv \in E(G)$	Number of edges
(2, 3)	3×2^n
(3, 4)	3×2^n
(3, 5)	$6 \times 2^n - 3$
(4, 5)	$9 \times 2^n - 6$
(5, 5)	$18 \times 2^n - 9$
(5, 6)	$9 \times 2^n - 6$

Theorem 1. The neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi index of a PAMAM dendrimer $PD_1[n]$ is

$$NKB(G) = (459 + 3\sqrt{13} + 6\sqrt{34} + 9\sqrt{41} + 90\sqrt{2} + 6\sqrt{61})2^n - 235 - 3\sqrt{34} - 6\sqrt{41} - 45\sqrt{2} - 6\sqrt{61}$$

Proof: Let $G = PD_1[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} NKB(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left((S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2} \right) \\ &= 3 \times 2^n \left((2+3) + \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2} \right) + 3 \times 2^n \left((3+4) + \sqrt{3^2 + 4^2} \right) \\ &\quad + (6 \times 2^n - 3) \left((3+5) + \sqrt{3^2 + 5^2} \right) \\ &\quad + (9 \times 2^n - 6) \left((4+5) + \sqrt{4^2 + 5^2} \right) \\ &\quad + (18 \times 2^n - 9) \left((5+5) + \sqrt{5^2 + 5^2} \right) \\ &\quad + (9 \times 2^n - 6) \left((5+6) + \sqrt{5^2 + 6^2} \right) \\ &= (459 + 3\sqrt{13} + 6\sqrt{34} + 9\sqrt{41} + 90\sqrt{2} + 6\sqrt{61})2^n - 235 - 3\sqrt{34} - 6\sqrt{41} - 45\sqrt{2} - 6\sqrt{61} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2. The neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi exponential of a PAMAM dendrimer $PD_1[n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned} NKB(G, x) &= 3 \times 2^n x^{5+\sqrt{13}} + 3 \times 2^n x^{12} \\ &\quad + (6 \times 2^n - 3)x^{8+\sqrt{34}} + (9 \times 2^n - 6)x^{9+\sqrt{41}} \\ &\quad + (18 \times 2^n - 9)x^{10+5\sqrt{2}} + (9 \times 2^n - 6)x^{11+\sqrt{61}} \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $G = PD_1[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} NKB(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{(S_G(u)+S_G(v))+\sqrt{S_G(u)^2+S_G(v)^2}} \\ &= 3 \times 2^n x^{(2+3)+\sqrt{2^2+3^2}} + 3 \times 2^n x^{(3+4)+\sqrt{3^2+4^2}} \\ &\quad + (6 \times 2^n - 3)x^{(3+5)+\sqrt{3^2+5^2}} + (9 \times 2^n - 6)x^{(4+5)+\sqrt{4^2+5^2}} \\ &\quad + (18 \times 2^n - 9)x^{(5+5)+\sqrt{5^2+5^2}} + (9 \times 2^n - 6)x^{(5+6)+\sqrt{5^2+6^2}} \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

Theorem 3. The modified neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi index of a PAMAM dendrimer $PD_1[n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NKB(G) &= \left(\frac{3}{5+\sqrt{13}} + \frac{3}{12} + \frac{6}{8+\sqrt{34}} + \frac{9}{9+\sqrt{41}} + \frac{18}{10+5\sqrt{2}} \right) 2^n \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{9}{11+\sqrt{61}} \right) 2^n - \frac{3}{8+\sqrt{34}} - \frac{6}{9+\sqrt{41}} - \frac{9}{10+5\sqrt{2}} \\ &\quad - \frac{6}{11+\sqrt{61}} \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $G = PD_1[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & {}^m NKB(G) \\ &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{(S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}} \\ &= \frac{3 \times 2^n}{(2+3) + \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2}} + \frac{3 \times 2^n}{(3+4) + \sqrt{3^2 + 4^2}} \\ &+ \frac{6 \times 2^n - 3}{(3+5) + \sqrt{3^2 + 5^2}} + \frac{9 \times 2^n - 6}{(4+5) + \sqrt{4^2 + 5^2}} \\ &+ \frac{18 \times 2^n - 9}{(5+5) + \sqrt{5^2 + 5^2}} + \frac{9 \times 2^n - 6}{(5+6) + \sqrt{5^2 + 6^2}}. \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

Theorem 4. The modified neighborhood Kepler Banhatti exponential of a PAMAM dendrimer $PD_1[n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & {}^m NKB(G) \\ &= 3 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{5+\sqrt{13}}} + 3 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{12}} + (6 \times 2^n - 3) x^{\frac{1}{8+\sqrt{34}}} \\ &+ (9 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{9+\sqrt{41}}} + (18 \times 2^n - 9) x^{\frac{1}{10+5\sqrt{2}}} \\ &+ (9 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{11+\sqrt{61}}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $G = PD_1[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & {}^m NKB(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{(S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}}} \\ &= 3 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{(2+3) + \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2}}} + 3 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{(3+4) + \sqrt{3^2 + 4^2}}} \\ &+ (6 \times 2^n - 3) x^{\frac{1}{(3+5) + \sqrt{3^2 + 5^2}}} + (9 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{(4+5) + \sqrt{4^2 + 5^2}}} \\ &+ (18 \times 2^n - 9) x^{\frac{1}{(5+5) + \sqrt{5^2 + 5^2}}} + (9 \times 2^n - 6) x^{\frac{1}{(5+6) + \sqrt{5^2 + 6^2}}}. \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

3. RESULTLYS FOR POPAM DENDRIMERS $POD_2[n]$

In this section, we focus on the molecular graph of POPAM dendrimers. This family of dendrimers is denoted by $POD_2[n]$, where n is the steps of growth in this type of dendrimers. The molecular graph of $POD_2[2]$ is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The molecular graph of $POD_2[n]$

Let G be the molecular graph of POPAM dendrimers $POD_2[n]$. By algebraic method, we obtain that $|V(POD_2[n])| = 2^{n+5} - 10$ and $|E(POD_2[n])| = 2^{n+5} - 11$. The edge partition of $POD_2[n]$ based on the degree sum of neighbors of end vertices of each edge is obtained as given in Table 2.

Table 2. Edge partition of $POD_2[n]$ based on $S_G(u)$ and $S_G(v)$

$S_G(u), S_G(v) \setminus uv \in E(G)$	Number of edges
(2, 3)	2^{n+2}
(3, 4)	2^{n+2}
(4, 4)	1
(4, 5)	$3 \times 2^n - 6$
(5, 6)	$3 \times 2^n - 6$

Theorem 5. The neighborhood Kepler Banhatti index of a POPAM dendrimer $POD_2[n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & NKB(G) \\ &= (12 + \sqrt{13}) \times 2^{n+2} + 60 \times 2^n + 8 + 4\sqrt{2} - 6\sqrt{41} - 6\sqrt{61}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $G = POD_2[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & NKB(G) \\ &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left((S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2} \right) \\ &= 2^{n+2} \left((2+3) + \sqrt{2^2 + 3^2} \right) + 2^{n+2} \left((3+4) + \sqrt{3^2 + 4^2} \right) \\ &+ 1 \left((4+4) + \sqrt{4^2 + 4^2} \right) \\ &+ (3 \times 2^n - 6) \left((4+5) + \sqrt{4^2 + 5^2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+(3 \times 2^n - 6)((5 + 6) + \sqrt{5^2 + 6^2}) \\
 &= (12 + \sqrt{13})2^{n+2} + 60 \times 2^n + 8 + 4\sqrt{2} - 6\sqrt{41} - 6\sqrt{61}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 6. The neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi exponential of a POPAM dendrimer $POD_2[n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
 NKB(G, x) &= 2^{n+2} x^{5+\sqrt{13}} + 2^{n+2} x^{12} \\
 &+ 1x^{8+4\sqrt{2}} + (3 \times 2^n - 6)x^{9+\sqrt{41}} + (3 \times 2^n - 6)x^{11+\sqrt{61}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $G = POD_2[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 NKB(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{(S_G(u)+S_G(v))+\sqrt{S_G(u)^2+S_G(v)^2}} \\
 &= 2^{n+2} x^{(2+3)+\sqrt{2^2+3^2}} + 2^{n+2} x^{(3+4)+\sqrt{3^2+4^2}} \\
 &+ 1x^{(4+4)+\sqrt{4^2+4^2}} + (3 \times 2^n - 6)x^{(4+5)+\sqrt{4^2+5^2}} \\
 &+ (3 \times 2^n - 6)x^{(5+6)+\sqrt{5^2+6^2}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

Theorem 7. The modified neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi index of a POPAM dendrimer $POD_2[n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m NKB(G) &= \left(\frac{1}{5 + \sqrt{13}} + \frac{1}{12} \right) 2^{n+2} + \left(\frac{3}{9 + \sqrt{41}} + \frac{3}{11 + \sqrt{61}} \right) 2^n \\
 &+ \frac{1}{8 + 4\sqrt{2}} - \frac{6}{9 + \sqrt{41}} - \frac{6}{11 + \sqrt{61}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $G = PD_1[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m NKB(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{(S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}} \\
 &= \frac{2^{n+2}}{(2+3) + \sqrt{2^2+3^2}} + \frac{2^{n+2}}{(3+4) + \sqrt{3^2+4^2}} \\
 &+ \frac{1}{(4+4) + \sqrt{4^2+4^2}} + \frac{3 \times 2^n - 6}{(4+5) + \sqrt{4^2+5^2}} \\
 &+ \frac{3 \times 2^n - 6}{(5+6) + \sqrt{5^2+6^2}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

Theorem 8. The modified neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi exponential of a POPAM dendrimer $POD_2[n]$ is

$${}^m NKB(G)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 2^{n+2} x^{\frac{1}{5+\sqrt{13}}} + 2^{n+2} x^{\frac{1}{12}} + 1x^{\frac{1}{8+4\sqrt{2}}} \\
 &+ (3 \times 2^n - 6)x^{\frac{1}{9+\sqrt{41}}} + (3 \times 2^n - 6)x^{\frac{1}{11+\sqrt{61}}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $G = PD_1[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m NKB(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{(S_G(u)+S_G(v))+\sqrt{S_G(u)^2+S_G(v)^2}}} \\
 &= 2^{n+2} x^{\frac{1}{(2+3)+\sqrt{2^2+3^2}}} + 2^{n+2} x^{\frac{1}{(3+4)+\sqrt{3^2+4^2}}} \\
 &+ 1x^{\frac{1}{(4+4)+\sqrt{4^2+4^2}}} + (3 \times 2^n - 6)x^{\frac{1}{(4+5)+\sqrt{4^2+5^2}}} \\
 &+ (3 \times 2^n - 6)x^{\frac{1}{(5+6)+\sqrt{5^2+6^2}}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

4. RESULTS FOR TETRATHIAFULVALENE DENDRIMERS $TD_2[n]$

In this section, we focus on the molecular graph of a tetrathiafulvalene dendrimer. This family of tetrathiafulvalene dendrimers is denoted by $TD_2[n]$, where n is the steps of growth in this type of dendrimers for $n \geq 0$. The molecular graph of $TD_2[2]$ is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The molecular graph of $TD_2[2]$

Let G be the molecular graph of tetrathiafulvalene dendrimers $TD_2[n]$. By algebraic method, we obtain that $|V(G)| = 31 \times 2^{n+2} - 74$ and $|E(G)| = 35 \times 2^{n+2} - 85$. Also the edge partition of $TD_2[n]$ based on the degree sum of neighbors of end vertices of each edge is obtained as given in Table 3

Table 3. Edge partition of $TD_2[n]$ based on $S_G(u)$ and $S_G(v)$

$S_G(u), S_G(v) \setminus uv \in E(G)$	Number of edges
(2, 4)	2^{n+2}

(3, 6)	$2^{n+2} - 4$
(4, 6)	2^{n+2}
(5, 5)	$7 \times 2^{n+2} - 16$
(5, 6)	$11 \times 2^{n+2} - 24$
(5, 7)	$3 \times 2^{n+2} - 8$
(6, 6)	$2^{n+2} - 4$
(6, 7)	$8 \times 2^{n+2} - 24$
(7, 7)	$2 \times 2^{n+2} - 5$

Theorem 9. The neighborhood Kepler Bhanhatti index of a dendrimer $TD_2[n]$ is

$$NKB(G) = (132 + 5\sqrt{5} + 55\sqrt{2} + 2\sqrt{13} + 11\sqrt{61} + 3\sqrt{74} + 8\sqrt{85})2^{n+2} - 986 - 12\sqrt{5} - 139\sqrt{2} - 24\sqrt{61} - 8\sqrt{74} - 24\sqrt{85}.$$

Proof: Let $G = TD_2[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} NKB(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left((S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2} \right) \\ &= 2^{n+2} \left((2+4) + \sqrt{2^2 + 4^2} \right) \\ &\quad + (2^{n+2} - 4) \left((3+6) + \sqrt{3^2 + 6^2} \right) \\ &\quad + 2^{n+2} \left((4+6) + \sqrt{4^2 + 6^2} \right) \\ &\quad + (7 \times 2^{n+2} - 16) \left((5+5) + \sqrt{5^2 + 5^2} \right) \\ &\quad + (11 \times 2^{n+2} - 24) \left((5+6) + \sqrt{5^2 + 6^2} \right) \\ &\quad + (3 \times 2^{n+2} - 8) \left((5+7) + \sqrt{5^2 + 7^2} \right) \\ &\quad + (2^{n+2} - 4) \left((6+6) + \sqrt{6^2 + 6^2} \right) \\ &\quad + (8 \times 2^{n+2} - 24) \left((6+7) + \sqrt{6^2 + 7^2} \right) \\ &\quad + (2 \times 2^{n+2} - 5) \left((7+7) + \sqrt{7^2 + 7^2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

Theorem 10. The neighborhood Kepler Bhanhatti exponential of a dendrimer $TD_2[n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned} NKB(G, x) &= 2^{n+2} x^{6+2\sqrt{5}} + (2^{n+2} - 4) x^{9+3\sqrt{5}} \\ &\quad + 2^{n+2} x^{10+2\sqrt{13}} + (7 \times 2^{n+2} - 16) x^{10+5\sqrt{2}} \\ &\quad + (11 \times 2^{n+2} - 24) x^{11+\sqrt{61}} + (3 \times 2^{n+2} - 8) x^{12+\sqrt{74}} \\ &\quad + (2^{n+2} - 4) x^{12+6\sqrt{2}} + (8 \times 2^{n+2} - 24) x^{13+\sqrt{85}} \\ &\quad + (2 \times 2^{n+2} - 5) x^{14+7\sqrt{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $G = TD_2[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} NKB(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{(S_G(u)+S_G(v))+\sqrt{S_G(u)^2+S_G(v)^2}} \\ &= 2^{n+2} x^{(2+4)+\sqrt{2^2+4^2}} + (2^{n+2} - 4) x^{(3+6)+\sqrt{3^2+6^2}} \\ &\quad + 2^{n+2} x^{(4+6)+\sqrt{4^2+6^2}} + (7 \times 2^{n+2} - 16) x^{(5+5)+\sqrt{5^2+5^2}} \\ &\quad + (11 \times 2^{n+2} - 24) x^{(5+6)+\sqrt{5^2+6^2}} \\ &\quad + (3 \times 2^{n+2} - 8) x^{(5+7)+\sqrt{5^2+7^2}} + (2^{n+2} - 4) x^{(6+6)+\sqrt{6^2+6^2}} \\ &\quad + (8 \times 2^{n+2} - 24) x^{(6+7)+\sqrt{6^2+7^2}} \\ &\quad + (2 \times 2^{n+2} - 5) x^{(7+7)+\sqrt{7^2+7^2}}. \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

Theorem 11. The modified neighborhood Kepler Bhanhatti index of a dendrimer $TD_2[n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NKB(G) &= \left(\frac{1}{6+2\sqrt{5}} + \frac{1}{9+3\sqrt{5}} + \frac{1}{10+2\sqrt{13}} + \frac{7}{10+5\sqrt{2}} \right) 2^{n+2} \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{11}{11+\sqrt{61}} + \frac{3}{12+\sqrt{74}} + \frac{1}{12+6\sqrt{2}} + \frac{8}{13+\sqrt{85}} \right) 2^{n+2} \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{2}{14+7\sqrt{2}} \right) 2^{n+2} - \frac{4}{9+3\sqrt{5}} - \frac{16}{10+5\sqrt{2}} - \frac{24}{11+\sqrt{61}} \\ &\quad - \frac{8}{12+\sqrt{74}} - \frac{4}{12+6\sqrt{2}} - \frac{24}{13+\sqrt{85}} - \frac{5}{14+7\sqrt{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $G = TD_2[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m NKB(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{(S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}} \\ &= \frac{2^{n+2}}{(2+4) + \sqrt{2^2 + 4^2}} + \frac{2^{n+2} - 4}{(3+6) + \sqrt{3^2 + 6^2}} \\ &\quad + \frac{2^{n+2}}{(4+6) + \sqrt{4^2 + 6^2}} + \frac{7 \times 2^{n+2} - 16}{(5+5) + \sqrt{5^2 + 5^2}} \\ &\quad + \frac{11 \times 2^{n+2} - 24}{(5+6) + \sqrt{5^2 + 6^2}} + \frac{3 \times 2^{n+2} - 8}{(5+7) + \sqrt{5^2 + 7^2}} \\ &\quad + \frac{2^{n+2} - 4}{(6+6) + \sqrt{6^2 + 6^2}} + \frac{8 \times 2^{n+2} - 24}{(6+7) + \sqrt{6^2 + 7^2}} \\ &\quad + \frac{2 \times 2^{n+2} - 5}{(7+7) + \sqrt{7^2 + 7^2}} \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

Theorem 12. The modified neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi exponential of a dendrimer $TD_2[n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m NKB(G) &= 2^{n+2} x^{\frac{1}{6+2\sqrt{5}}} + (2^{n+2} - 4) 2^{n+2} x^{\frac{1}{9+3\sqrt{5}}} + 2^{n+2} x^{\frac{1}{10+2\sqrt{13}}} \\
 &+ (7 \times 2^{n+2} - 16) x^{\frac{1}{10+5\sqrt{2}}} + (11 \times 2^{n+2} - 24) x^{\frac{1}{11+\sqrt{61}}} \\
 &+ (3 \times 2^{n+2} - 8) x^{\frac{1}{12+\sqrt{74}}} + (2^{n+2} - 4) x^{\frac{1}{12+6\sqrt{2}}} \\
 &+ (8 \times 2^{n+2} - 24) x^{\frac{1}{13+\sqrt{85}}} + (2 \times 2^{n+2} - 5) x^{\frac{1}{14+7\sqrt{2}}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $G = TD_2[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^m NKB(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{(S_G(u)+S_G(v))+\sqrt{S_G(u)^2+S_G(v)^2}}} \\
 &= 2^{n+2} x^{\frac{1}{(2+4)+\sqrt{2^2+4^2}}} + (2^{n+2} - 4) 2^{n+2} x^{\frac{1}{(3+6)+\sqrt{3^2+6^2}}} \\
 &+ 2^{n+2} x^{\frac{1}{(4+6)+\sqrt{4^2+6^2}}} + (7 \times 2^{n+2} - 16) x^{\frac{1}{(5+5)+\sqrt{5^2+5^2}}} \\
 &+ (11 \times 2^{n+2} - 24) x^{\frac{1}{(5+6)+\sqrt{5^2+6^2}}} + (3 \times 2^{n+2} - 8) x^{\frac{1}{(5+7)+\sqrt{5^2+7^2}}} \\
 &+ (2^{n+2} - 4) x^{\frac{1}{(6+6)+\sqrt{6^2+6^2}}} + (8 \times 2^{n+2} - 24) x^{\frac{1}{(6+7)+\sqrt{6^2+7^2}}} \\
 &+ (2 \times 2^{n+2} - 5) x^{\frac{1}{(7+7)+\sqrt{7^2+7^2}}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

5. RESULTS FOR $NS_2[n]$ DENDRIMERS

In this section, we focus on the class of $NS_2[n]$ dendrimers with $n \geq 1$. The graph of $NS_2[2]$ is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The graph of $NS_2[2]$

Let G be the graph of $NS_2[n]$ dendrimers. By algebraic method, we obtain that $|V(G)|=16 \times 2^n - 4$ and $|E(G)|=18 \times 2^n - 5$. Also the edge partition of $NS_2[n]$ based on the degree sum of neighbors of end vertices of each edge is obtained as given in Table 4.

Table 4. Edge partition of $NS_2[n]$ based on $S_G(u)$ and $S_G(v)$

$S_G(u), S_G(v) \setminus uv \in E(G)$	Number of edges
(4, 4)	2×2^n
(5, 4)	2×2^n
(5, 5)	$2 \times 2^n + 2$
(5, 6)	6×2^n
(7, 7)	1
(5, 7)	4
(6, 6)	$6 \times 2^n - 12$

Theorem 13. The neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi index of a dendrimer $NS_2[n]$ is

$$NKB(G) = (192 + 54\sqrt{2} + 2\sqrt{41} + 6\sqrt{61}) 2^n - 69 - 55\sqrt{2} + 4\sqrt{74}.$$

Proof: Let $G = NS_2[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 NKB(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left((S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2} \right) \\
 &= 2 \times 2^n \left((4+4) + \sqrt{4^2+4^2} \right) + 2 \times 2^n \left((5+4) + \sqrt{5^2+4^2} \right) \\
 &+ (2 \times 2^n + 2) \left((5+5) + \sqrt{5^2+5^2} \right) \\
 &+ 6 \times 2^n \left((5+6) + \sqrt{5^2+6^2} \right) \\
 &+ 1 \left((7+7) + \sqrt{7^2+7^2} \right) + 4 \left((5+7) + \sqrt{5^2+7^2} \right) \\
 &+ (6 \times 2^n - 12) \left((6+6) + \sqrt{6^2+6^2} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result

Theorem 14. The neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi exponential of a dendrimer $NS_2[n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
 NKB(G, x) &= 2 \times 2^n x^{8+4\sqrt{2}} + 2 \times 2^n x^{9+\sqrt{41}} \\
 &+ (2 \times 2^n + 2) x^{10+5\sqrt{2}} + 6 \times 2^n x^{11+\sqrt{61}} \\
 &+ 1 x^{14+7\sqrt{2}} + 4 x^{12+\sqrt{74}} + (6 \times 2^n - 12) x^{12+6\sqrt{2}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $G = NS_2[n]$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 NKB(G, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{(S_G(u)+S_G(v))+\sqrt{S_G(u)^2+S_G(v)^2}}} \\
 &= 2 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{(4+4)+\sqrt{4^2+4^2}}} + 2 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{(5+4)+\sqrt{5^2+4^2}}} \\
 &+ (2 \times 2^n + 2) x^{\frac{1}{(5+5)+\sqrt{5^2+5^2}}} + 6 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{(5+6)+\sqrt{5^2+6^2}}} \\
 &+ 1 x^{\frac{1}{(7+7)+\sqrt{7^2+7^2}}} + 4 x^{\frac{1}{(5+7)+\sqrt{5^2+7^2}}} \\
 &+ (6 \times 2^n - 12) x^{\frac{1}{(6+6)+\sqrt{6^2+6^2}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result

Theorem 15. The modified neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi index of a POPAM dendrimer $POD_2[n]$ is

$${}^m NKB(G) = \left(\frac{1}{4+2\sqrt{2}} + \frac{2}{9+\sqrt{41}} + \frac{2}{10+5\sqrt{2}} + \frac{6}{11+\sqrt{61}} \right) 2^n + \left(\frac{1}{2+\sqrt{2}} \right) 2^n + \frac{1}{7+7\sqrt{2}} + \frac{4}{12+\sqrt{74}} - \frac{2}{2+\sqrt{2}}.$$

Proof: Let $G = NS_2[n]$. We have

$${}^m NKB(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{(S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}} = \frac{2 \times 2^n}{(4+4) + \sqrt{4^2 + 4^2}} + \frac{2 \times 2^n}{(5+4) + \sqrt{5^2 + 4^2}} + \frac{2 \times 2^n + 2}{(5+5) + \sqrt{5^2 + 5^2}} + \frac{6 \times 2^n}{(5+6) + \sqrt{5^2 + 6^2}} + \frac{1}{(7+7) + \sqrt{7^2 + 7^2}} + \frac{4}{(5+7) + \sqrt{5^2 + 7^2}} + \frac{6 \times 2^n - 12}{(6+6) + \sqrt{6^2 + 6^2}}.$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

Theorem 16. The modified neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi exponential of a POPAM dendrimer $POD_2[n]$ is

$${}^m NKB(G) = 2 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{8+4\sqrt{2}}} + 2 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{9+\sqrt{41}}} + (2 \times 2^n + 2) x^{\frac{1}{10+5\sqrt{2}}} + (2 \times 2^n + 2) x^{\frac{1}{10+5\sqrt{2}}} + 6 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{11+\sqrt{61}}} + 1 x^{\frac{1}{14+7\sqrt{2}}} + 4 x^{\frac{1}{12+\sqrt{74}}} + (6 \times 2^n - 12) x^{\frac{1}{12+6\sqrt{2}}}.$$

Proof: Let $G = NS_2[n]$. We have

$${}^m NKB(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{(S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2}}} = 2 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{(4+4) + \sqrt{4^2 + 4^2}}} + 2 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{(5+4) + \sqrt{5^2 + 4^2}}} + (2 \times 2^n + 2) x^{\frac{1}{(5+5) + \sqrt{5^2 + 5^2}}} + 6 \times 2^n x^{\frac{1}{(5+6) + \sqrt{5^2 + 6^2}}} + 1 x^{\frac{1}{(7+7) + \sqrt{7^2 + 7^2}}} + 4 x^{\frac{1}{(5+7) + \sqrt{5^2 + 7^2}}}$$

$$+ (6 \times 2^n - 12) x^{\frac{1}{(6+6) + \sqrt{6^2 + 6^2}}}.$$

By simplifying the above equation, we obtain the desired result.

6. PROPERTIES OF THE TEMPERATURE ELLIPTIC SOMBOR INDEX

Theorem 17. Let G be a connected graph. Then

$$\sqrt{2} NM_1(G) \leq TNKB(G) < 2 NM_1(G).$$

Proof: For any two positive numbers a and b ,

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(a+b) \leq \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} < a+b.$$

$$\sqrt{2}(a+b) \leq (a+b) + \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} < 2(a+b)$$

For $a = S_G(u)$ and $b = S_G(v)$, the above inequality becomes

$$\sqrt{2}(S_G(u) + S_G(v)) \leq (S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{(S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2)} < 2(S_G(u) + S_G(v))$$

By the definitions, we have

$$\sqrt{2} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (S_G(u) + S_G(v)) \leq \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left((S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2} \right) < 2 \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (S_G(u) + S_G(v))$$

Thus we get the desired result.

Theorem 18. Let G be a connected graph. Then

$$NKB(G) = NM_1(G) + NSO(G).$$

Proof: We have

$$\sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left((S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2} \right) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (S_G(u) + S_G(v)) + \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{S_G(u)^2 + S_G(v)^2} = NM_1(G) + NSO(G)$$

7. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have introduced the neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi index, modified neighborhood Kepler Bhanthi index of a graph. We have computed these indices and their corresponding exponentials of certain families of dendrimers.

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